

→ Dear Conservatives, stop saying there is no such thing as Systemic Racism!¹

POS 2.0 - Found: the Systemic/Institutional Racism the left and liberals have been looking for: the Democrat Party/DNC

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¹ Figure 1 - The “Tarantino Code”; a guide to the real Systemic Racism everyone has been looking for; credit: “Django Unchained”

ABSTRACT

The rise of the Democratic Party in the 1800s² was a direct reflection of racism in the Southern South. The Ku Klux Klan was a terrorist organization³ created to illegally enforce political control over the freedmen population in a postbellum society. The refusal to pass the Civil Rights Act of 1871⁴ was a Democratic effort.⁵ Furthermore, there was no massive agreement/switch between the two parties⁶. There were two senators who defected⁷, and the party colors flip-flopped for cultural reasons.⁸ In point of fact, even in the 1930s the Democrats (especially FDR⁹) had an unusually cordial relationship with Hitler's Nationalist Socialist Party.¹⁰ Prior to that they had a lot of sympathy for, and tolerance, for the Bolsheviks and "Progressives" of the Soviet Communist era, well before Stalin took power. It is only natural that some of these "lefties" (with right-hemispheric leanings) would continue to maintain¹¹ that we have never seen "real communism" as "Marx envisioned it," because the sympathies of the 1920s were *not* what was imported to America openly in the 1950s. Rather, the "Critical Theorists" of the 1950s had more in common¹² with the Soviet Communist reactionaries (to Nazis) than to Bolshevism. However, the early ideas of Lenin, reiterated in the 1960s by John Lennon in his song "Dreamer," revitalized a leftist utopian ideal, that simply never was and never will be. Democrats in the 1960s were lying to their voters.

The actual roots of the Democrat Party are steeped in racist policies, such as concealed carry permits, Jim Crow laws, "Separate But Equal," (which is a new favorite of Black Lives Matter®, Inc.), and of course the KKK¹³. Worse, the threat of violence was also faced by political rivals who sought to undo this, and we find cases in history where even white Republicans were targeted - in the 1800s just as today - for standing with African Americans, and against Systemic Racism. Today the SR is so endemic, that platitudes about 'poor' people (who are "just as smart as White People"¹⁴) not being able to get voter ID or driver's licenses¹⁵ are still very common among media pundits and political machinists; especially race hustlers like Stacey Abrams or Al Sharpton. In this paper, the author briefly explores this history with some chronology and a plethora of historical citations. If it is upsetting, then the bitter medicine is working.

² By none other than the racist POS, Andrew Jackson himself, in 1828; famous of course for the Trail of Tears. His one good quality was he ran out the central banks, the irony of which is the Federal Reserve and Democrats made sure his face was on the \$20 bill, as an insult to him and a reminder of the power of the colonial south.

³ In the true sense of the meaning of the word "terrorist." You know, before the radical Left tried to redefine it as gun-toting Trump-voting patriots who support the Constitution.

⁴

<https://www.ojp.gov/ncjrs/virtual-library/abstracts/review-civil-rights-act-1871-42-usc-1983-correctional-personnel#:~:text=The%201871%20Civil%20Rights%20Act.the%20constitutional%20rights%20of%20another.>

⁵ <https://cpb-us-e1.wpmucdn.com/sites.usc.edu/dist/2/77/files/2018/01/demise-v2q5de.pdf>

⁶ <https://areomagazine.com/2019/04/03/the-party-switch-myth/>

⁷ <https://www.amazon.com/United-States-Socialism-Behind-Evil/dp/1250163781>

⁸ [CRUSHING FACTS: D'Souza proves this leftist wrong, the big switch is a myth](#)

⁸ <https://www.smithsonianmag.com/history/when-republicans-were-blue-and-democrats-were-red-104176297/>

⁹ <https://www.jstor.org/stable/25080976>

¹⁰ <https://www.cato.org/commentary/hitler-mussolini-roosevelt>

¹¹ Despite the data from 1919-2019 showing otherwise https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/History_of_communism

¹² Hence the way Antifa looks and behaves like "Brown Shirts"

¹³ https://history.house.gov/Historical-Highlights/1851-1900/hh_1871_04_20_KKK_Act/

¹⁴ President Joe Biden, on the campaign road as former Vice President.

¹⁵ [Ami Horowitz: How white liberals really view black voters](#)

Tories, Whigs, And Race-hustlers - the Antebellum South

Tories were British loyalists¹⁶. Historically in England Whigs were supporters of parliament and expansionism. It can be said, in a lot of ways that the rivalry of the British parties bleeding over to America was one of the worst holdovers of colonialism (outside of slavery). It was done, despite the warnings of George Washington¹⁷. Parties themselves should have been abolished by the federal amendment, but alas, they were not. And the result: the two-party nightmare continued in America through the Exclusion Crisis right to the modern day..

“During the Exclusion Crisis, the Whigs were seen as political revisionists, activist politicians willing to risk political turmoil in their opposition to the legitimate monarch, while Tories were political loyalists.”¹⁸

The key to understanding the modern problem, is to understand that although the Tories have been replaced (as conservatives) by the Republican party, and continue still to support nationalism, rather than traditional Americanism (now called Libertarianism), the Whigs morphed from federalist supporters, in terms of the Legislative, to the supporters of executive power. This strongly explains the strain of Executive power from the mid-1800s right through Harry Truman, and more recently the Obama/Biden regimes. The tendency to rely on governmental power is a key part to truly understand. Because while it is en vogue *now* for Democrats to support anti-whiteism, it was the habit of the Federalists, and even Lincoln, in the past when supporting government power, and/or nation building, to oppress first the Native tribes (especially: A. Jackson) and then after the Civil War, the freed black men. It was a struggle from the get-go for freedmen to attain voting rights, (hence the 3/5 rule¹⁹), and naturally for black women to receive their voting rights even after the suffragettes - who were by in large very racist, though empathetic - to receive *their* due rights.

Lincoln’s Republican Party... the enemy of slaves?!?

No, Lincoln’s party... the Grand Old Party, as it is sometimes called... is not the enemy of black people. It isn’t a great ally, either. However, it isn’t hard to see how the GOP went from (Lincoln included) disabusing native tribes for national power, to turning the other direction as the pro-government-power party - the Democrats - began to disabuse the American citizens. That is both freedmen and white descendents and participants in abolitionism. Why? Because it fed the national power-infrastructure in order to compromise with the part of Systemic Racism: the DNC.

Democrats in the 20th Century: Eugenicide as a Rule

From an early period the Democrats were known as a “party of the gentry.” Who else could get women’s suffrage done (and would care), except white, well-to-do women? That is precisely the main group that the party *still* mostly caters to, from The View (and their particular form of misanthropist anti-white male reactionary behaviors) to the Clinton Foundation, et al. The party courts dominant male power, particular white male patriarchs (rather like the gentrified South) at the highest echelons, and has a strain of particular

¹⁶ <https://www.britannica.com/topic/loyalist>

¹⁷ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/George_Washington%27s_Farewell_Address

¹⁸ <https://mason.gmu.edu/~ayadav/historical%20outline/whig%20and%20tory.htm>

¹⁹ (1787) <https://www.britannica.com/topic/three-fifths-compromise>

patriarchism. It says “you are OUR ally, or you ain’t black.”²⁰ That’s racist, of course, but it isn’t much different than the plantation system.²¹

Now among these suffragettes, who had their own particular or peculiar views on “how to help brown and black women” was a propensity to believe in both birth control/abortion, *and* in eugenics. That is: they saw them as inferior and incapable of helping themselves.²² Just as Planned Parenthood and the DNC today. Margaret Sanger did not see herself as a “racist.” She saw herself as a liberator of women descended from slavery. However, this peculiar form of paternalism coming from the suffragettes was couched under the auspices of evangelical Christianity - and this strikes hard to the point: that Malthusianism is an anti-Lockean value. Like Marxism, it professes a form of compassion for the masses which the Democrat Party already catered to, and has always had a weakness for, so long as they were whites, and/or blacks that vote for whites. So we see today strange bedfellows of complete paradox within the Democrat-targeted voting demographic, who is inculcated along racist lines and taught to hate Republicans. These paradoxes include Muslims *and* gays, and strangely enough gays that profess to love Islam. It includes feminists and trans, even though they work at odds with each other. It includes conservative latinos, and neoliberal zionist Jews who absolutely do not want Latinos in their neighborhoods, but do not mind if they stream across the borders in untold numbers to vote for their favorite zionists, and/or Marxists (eg: Bernie). The GOP favors National power, to its detriment, but the DNC simply favors power, and anybody is a good body, even if it is already cold and dead. What matters is the power of the vote, and this isn’t new for the Democrats because it is the behavior of the Whigs back when all the “power” was from whites. Once blacks were taught they *had* to vote Democrat, and they do 90% of the time²³, then sure, it was A-OK to give them the vote and even civil rights. Not without interference, though: such as forced bussing, integration laws, welfare, and affirmative action; all of which destroyed black-owned, created markets, communities, banking, stock markets, businesses, and of course the family.

In the end, it was the eugenicide that remains to this day of primarily black babies since Roe v Wade²⁴, that has further enabled continued destruction of the black nuclear family²⁵, and the lifting and support of a three-tier apartheid:

- At the top: white gentry operators, such as the Bidens and Clintons; with some African-American race hustlers that have demonstrated they don’t really care about black issues²⁶ (like the Obamas²⁷.)
- In the middle: black race-hustling operatives - the “house negroes”²⁸ of politics, such as Rev. Jackson, Al Sharpton, Stacey Abrams, and the women of “The View.”
 - This is an important layer because it is they who assert and decide how the messaging happens as to who owns black people, and black votes.
- At the bottom: middle and poor-class blacks **who. never. left. the. mental. plantation.**

²⁰ Again, President Biden.

²¹ The RNC courts contractual and different forms of power relating to the Constitution and justice system; meanwhile the DNC courts media, academia, etc. They both court corporate power, because that is what the UCC legal system favors. But the biggest names in big tech associate with Democrats; and they love to control minds. Outside of Murdoch’s Fox News, which has definitely fallen into the hands of neocons and neolibs, most of the media, by far is blue owned.

²² The BLM riots and public debates were great times to see examples of white, ‘liberal’ women telling black people not to talk to Proud Boys, MAGA people, conservative news, or, in some cases: at all. ^ And in one instance it was pointed out at the time

²³ 88-93% <https://www.nytimes.com/2020/09/16/magazine/black-vote.html>

²⁴ https://www.health.ny.gov/statistics/vital_statistics/2017/table19.htm

<https://www.congress.gov/115/meeting/house/106562/witnesses/HHRG-115-JU10-Wstate-ParkerS-20171101-SD001.pdf>

²⁵ <https://www.city-journal.org/html/black-family-40-years-lies-12872.html>

²⁶ <https://www.newsweek.com/hbcu-funding-falls-45-billion-2-billion-under-latest-biden-spending-plan-1635870>

²⁷ <https://www.cnn.com/2016/06/30/politics/why-black-america-may-be-relieved-to-see-obama-go/index.html>

²⁸ <https://ccnmtl.columbia.edu/projects/mmt/mxp/speeches/mxa17.html>

The groups that are excluded from this are the rich or wealthy blacks who may pander (like Lebron James), or may stay silent (like Michael Jordan) but clearly who do well (like Oprah); and the black republicans who do just fine to quite well, running businesses and thinking for themselves. Which, of course the “black community” as it is mainstreamed, cannot abide, and attacks relentlessly (while ignoring the first group, for whom they demand and want money from), as well as **Democrat-only representation in public**, no matter what they support behind closed doors (like Dave Chapelle ;). Hence the *first* issue the mainstream had with a man like Kanye West.²⁹ It wasn’t that his hat was redneck or racist; it was neither. It was that it was “off message” from the Democratic Plantation.

The Mockery of the Civil Rights Act of 1963: the anti-MIMS of Welfarism

Thomas Sowell³⁰ is the top black academic and economist of the 20th (and now 21st) century. He began as a Marxist in belief, even radicalized, and then, after reviewing the data and facts and **thinking**, he realized the error of his beliefs.³¹ It is in fact completely the case that Welfarism has been an anti-MIMS for the black community, leaving it exposed to the relatively unsafe MIMS of gangs, drugs, and rap music. Why was welfarism, part of the “War on Poverty” done? Was it purely altruistic, or did President L. Johnson know what would happen? There are arguments for both sides, but we can see from the man’s own words the same strain of patriarchal views that was already described, when it came to blacks:

“There’s no question that Lyndon Johnson, despite championing the landmark Civil Rights Act of 1964 and signing it into law, was also a sometime racist and notorious vulgarian who rarely shied away from using the N-word in private. For example, he reportedly referred to the Civil Rights Act of 1957 as the “nigger bill” in more than one private phone conversation with Senate colleagues. And he reportedly said upon appointing African-American judge Thurgood Marshall to the Supreme Court, “Son, when I appoint a nigger to the court, I want everyone to know he’s a nigger.”³²

“These Negroes, they’re getting pretty uppity these days and that’s a problem for us since they’ve got something now they never had before, the political pull to back up their uppityness. Now we’ve got to do something about this, we’ve got to give them a little something, just enough to quiet them down, not enough to make a difference. For if we don’t move at all, then their allies will line up against us and there’ll be no way of stopping them, we’ll lose the filibuster and there’ll be no way of putting a brake on all sorts of wild legislation. It’ll be Reconstruction all over again.”

Affirmative Action & Reparations: anti-MIMS on steroids for Black America

AA has had, according to Sowell’s research³³, a specific and measurable negative impact on Black America. At this point, the data is clear and the government should stop welfarism and AA point blank. Instead the race hucksters and hustlers are pushing for the next level: reparations. What for isn’t clear. Who for isn’t clear. From who isn’t clear. Why isn’t even clear, nor simple. The fact is that African-Americans no more

²⁹ During the course of writing this article, but before the event, Kanye announced on the Alex Jones show he “likes Hitler.” He insisted he wasn’t being edgy... the author does not like Hitler **at all**; but it does seem that Kanye is either bipolar or something else, unmedicated, and has been hanging out with rabid anti-semites.

³⁰ <https://www.tsowell.com/writings.html>

³¹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Thomas_Sowell

³² <https://www.snopes.com/fact-check/lbj-voting-democratic/>

³³ <https://www.commentary.org/articles/thomas-sowell-2/affirmative-action-a-worldwide-disaster/>
<https://www.stephenhicks.org/wp-content/uploads/2018/01/Sowell-Affirmative-Action-Disaster-text.pdf>

deserve reparations at this stage - from slavery - than the Aztecs deserve new pyramids. The past is the past, and no one alive today was even a grandchild of those who were enslaved. So the real issue is money, and power. That's the entire game, and to pretend otherwise is an exercise in "catch me being Stupid." Who has time for these nonsense games when we can see what the impact of such a greedy, self-centered, and dangerous experiment it would be: the complete destruction of Black America and its future, through the elimination of assets? For every bankruptcy, one more poor person created to satisfy the greed of groups 1 & 2 mentioned before... on the backs of the 3rd group!

Lies, Damned Lies, and Conservative Lies - Neocon//RINO Hell

Why do conservatives, even Thomas Sowell and Larry Elder, continue to promote the lie that blacks all feel *must be a lie*? They live the Truth and *their truth* is that the system targets them. But who is targeting them? It's easy to pick and see the police³⁴, rather than a scarier truth: the Police State. What does the Police State represent? It represents nothing short of the *dogs* of the plantations which hound those who run away from the system itself; just like the Underground Railroad. It represents mental, economic, and physical control. Limitations, placed upon black descendents who *willingly* identify themselves with that system; those who are ignorant of:

- The Law & Juris Prudence
- Due process
- Legal recourse
- Financial mechanisms
- Business practices
- Corporate linguistics
- The English language (hence: the promotion of ebonics)
- Rationalism (which is needed to win cases)
- Logic (hence: the promotion of hatred of math, whites of the past, and philosophy)
- Ethics (hence: the promotion of lower standards for behavior and criminal justice)

In short, the anti-whiteism is not merely racism masquerading as anti-racism, a form of Orwellian mind-control. It is actually a *designed form of Marxist programming* which ties back to the Malthusian "turn of the century" eugenicidal maniacs. And the only way for it to continue to work is if controlled opposition fails to call it out. Not that Sowell and Elder are that controlled opposition (not like Fox News). But if the entire RINO/Neocon system which has very successful blacks (like C. Rice and C. Powell) fails to educate other blacks about the factual system of control and power the DNC has over its plantations of mind-controlled voters who are destroying nuclear families³⁵ and small business (literally in the case of Black Lives Matter © led riots)... it must be for a reason.

Outside of money being exchanged to keep quiet, what reason could there be? The main one is *cooperation* and *compromise*. And what do both parties tend to agree about, with vagaries of "how much" (besides gun control and abortion?): military and police contracts. In other words, the GOP's corruption by being so in bed with big military and big oil *mirrors* the control mechanisms of the DNC being in bed with big

³⁴ As the author showed, this happens because there is a spike in negative encounters *if* you divide the number of incidents by the population of black Americans, rather than ALL Americans. Naturally, if you live in a black neighborhood, that's how you will see your world. [📺 Cops and Blacks - What Liberals won't Hear](#)

³⁵ <https://www.politifact.com/article/2020/aug/28/ask-politifact-does-black-lives-matter-aim-destroy/>

tech/data and big pharma/food. Which has been shown to be a factual, and fascist connection (think: Tuskegee syphilis experiment, etc.) which utilizes black people as perpetual mind-slaves, and defacto chattel for corporatocratic oligarchy!

The czars are political scions - like the Clintons - and their 'Gestapo' is the hacktivist wings of the Democrat Party. And all the lobbyists and fundraisers who bilk the constituency for campaign money, while simultaneously feeding them lies and race-baiting and hatred. This hatred is manufactured in propaganda, like the '1619 Project'³⁶ and "White Fragility"³⁷ and forms a further barrier around the individual, who already has to struggle against the natural *dukkha* (ignorant-suffering) of life. Comedians like Chris Rock tried to tell them³⁸, but by then, it is too late. And the RNC et al is complicit in this the *same way* that the North was the industrial users of Southern slavery-led agriculture and products. It's a Triangle Trade of unholy evil, set in a modern landscape of corporate greed and consumerism, and its products are propaganda, hatred, and growing distrust of whites and even now Martin Luther King Jr.³⁹ or anyone that purports the ideals of Egalitarianism!⁴⁰

Democratic Socialism: Equal Misery, and Injustice, For All

The drumbeat of "equity" stems first from a central promise⁴¹ in the lies of lying liars like Karl Marx: that we can *create* equality. Well, we cannot. We can only create legal equality of opportunity, and then educate people against bigotry and also against lacking common sense by accepting the unacceptable⁴². All justice is individual, for an individual is the greatest minority of all⁴³ - and infants and fetuses are the most vulnerable of these. The creation of economic equality can only be had, in the first iteration of capitalism, by eliminating lack of resources. This only happens if everyone - save the most powerful at the top - becomes **equally poor**. That is exactly what will happen in a plastic world built by oligarchs to make them data, power and wealth. Then to rob everyone else of opportunities via red tape and critical (hypercritical) systemically enforced limitations aka "equity" design to raise people above one another based on immutable, intrinsic characteristics.

The curious thing is why all the System continues to promote to black people that they are short-changed in every 'factual' way except one: the truth about IQ and its connections to violence and dealing with situations in one's life, which can enable freedom or bring one a lifetime of Hell. Why does academia/trashademia hide this fact? Surely it is racist to tell someone that they cannot handle this truth, and the other factor of it: the lower IQ in African-Americans and Native-Americans is a manufactured situation, clearly the product of bad government policies⁴⁴. Through technology, chess, and education⁴⁵ actually you can, generation by generation, adaptation by DNA alteration, slowly increase this average without ethnic

³⁶ <https://www.forbes.com/sites/marybethgasman/2021/06/03/what-history-professors-really-think-about-the-1619-project/>

³⁷ <https://www.npr.org/2020/07/20/892943728/professor-criticizes-book-white-fragility-as-dehumanizing-to-black-people>

³⁸ Chris Rock - Black People VS. Niggaz (Bring the Pain 1996)

³⁹ <https://www.foxbusiness.com/kudlow/kudlow-woke-progressives-martin-luther-king>

⁴⁰ <https://www.jstor.org/stable/20027738>

⁴¹ Postmodernism and Cultural Marxism | Jordan B Peterson Isn't it interesting that the top results in Google assert cultural Marxism doesn't even exist, and to question all of these Critical Theories (since the 1950s) is an "alt-right" or "anti-semitic" "conspiracy theory." Well, Dufresne gives the entire history of the Critical Theories in social sciences in his work "On the Uniqueness of Western Civilization." It isn't a theory, it's a conspiracy fact.

⁴² Such as sexualizing/grooming children.

⁴³

<https://www.cambridge.org/core/journals/social-philosophy-and-policy/article/progressive-era-assault-on-individualism-and-property-rights/AF0CC8F6EF202C4C06ABAB956CD3CD1B>

⁴⁴ IQ vs Homicide by race

⁴⁵ <https://www.amazon.com/How-Increase-IQ-Discover-Intelligence/dp/1530459745>

<https://www.amazon.com/Complete-Idiots-Guide-Improving-Your/dp/0028627245>

cleansing/dilution. But it has never been in the interests of the DNC or Federal government, respectively, to do so. That is it.

All the other races will increase their IQs, unless they be curtailed (such as the white population-control agenda, and use of drugs to create a true “idiocracy”), so long as they interact with capitalistic opportunities and technologies... and mingle DNA (as the case seems to be.) This is evolutionary. All the devolution *must come* from either a chemical castration, (or abortive genocide of the geniuses found naturally), or from systemic population and mind control programs. Who did mind control? The Nazis and then CIA (Operation Paperclip⁴⁶) in Project MK-ULTRA⁴⁷ and Project KUBARK⁴⁸. These programs are not over, they are simply evolved.

Equity as a lie built to rebirth Segregation; What Useful Idiots Don't Know

The main outcome of the DNC support of ‘equity’ so far - the main product and service outside of riots, looting, and BLM stealing funds meant for helping black communities⁴⁹ - appears to be oddball examples of segregation⁵⁰. The saddest part of this segregation is that while the person becomes a defacto racist in demanding white people leave “People of Color Spaces”, which are not a thing, they let themselves down, and those of the civil rights era, while honestly isolating themselves from the rest of the working world. So, for example, when the young black woman is raging against the young white men⁵¹ who are using a campus table to do homework⁵², she is thinking she is standing up to someone, something, or some structure of oppression. She might even feel that she’s earning virtue points for this ‘brave’ act of racism. But in fact she is advertising to the future workforce that she is a drama queen, full of trouble, probably a future lawsuit or liability, and it’s best to stay away from her. She is limiting her opportunities.

Similarly, when the black principal of a Georgia school segregated black kids⁵³, thinking she could arrange for easier homework grades or results, she was robbing the black kids of opportunities to work with other races, and even creating the conditions of an echo chamber, which would only hamper those children as they head out into the real world. Both incidents were, of course, illegal under Federal Law, and they were handled. The latter had an African American parent turn the school in, as she understood *Brown v Board of Education* and what segregation means. But what if the radical regressive “progressives”, programmed by the Marxism of the Malthusian early 20th century, got their way and changed this law, or created an amendment to create “Separate but Equitable?” It would be the end of equality of opportunity and the beginning of civil strife and war. The Useful Idiots do not know, this is precisely what the radical Marxists, cultural or otherwise, particularly anarcho-communists, want. They want burning neighborhoods and businesses and lies in the news

⁴⁶ <https://documents2.theblackvault.com/documents/fbifiles/operationpaperclip-fbi1.pdf>

⁴⁷ <https://www.intelligence.senate.gov/sites/default/files/hearings/95mkultra.pdf>
<https://info.publicintelligence.net/CIA-MKULTRA-IG.pdf> <https://info.publicintelligence.net/SSCI-MKULTRA-1977.pdf>
https://www.cia.gov/library/abbottabad-compound/12/129E144131F2E093FB1E441C737ACF92_SearchForTheManchuriaCandidate.rtf.pdf

⁴⁸ <https://nsarchive2.gwu.edu/NSAEBB/NSAEBB122/CIA%20Kubark%201-60.pdf>

⁴⁹

<https://www.nbcnews.com/news/nbcblk/black-lives-matter-activists-accuse-executive-stealing-10-million-dono-rcna46481>

⁵⁰ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=fMnmzyBMLo0>

⁵¹ <https://www.yahoo.com/video/asu-students-harassed-multicultural-center-150628460.html>

⁵²

<https://www.dailymail.co.uk/video/news/video-2110472/Video-Racist-student-says-white-people-arent-allowed-study-center.html>

⁵³ <https://nypost.com/2021/08/11/mom-says-atlanta-school-racially-segregated-daughter-lawsuit/>

about the sources, so they can use these “crises” to do as Rep. Alexandria Ocasio-Cortez⁵⁴ said, “We’re going to ‘run train’ on the progressive agenda.”⁵⁵

This is a euphemism for gang-forced rape of a woman. She probably knew this⁵⁶. It’s still, in the end analysis, a surprisingly accurate description of what the Democrat Party is doing to America on behalf of cultural Marxism, and has been doing to African-Americans for over 150 years. She is an enabler of that rape. Minorities will be the primary sufferers, and that includes white Appalachians, individualists, and many others.

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